

CORONA VIRUS - THE REAL VACCINE

INTRODUCTION

This text is based on the wisdom from the oldest writings on the planet Earth. The Vedas are known to be the first scriptures of human kind.

Hence in the Yoga Vasishtha in IV:22 it is stated :-

He sees the Truth who sees that the non-dual consciousness (of Mother Nature), which indwells in all beings, is omnipotent and omnipresent.

He is unaffected who knows that pleasure, pain, birth, death, health and disease etc. are all the Self (Mother Nature).

Therefore readers may not understand the text below, nor believe in it. However, **please pass it on to others**; because you do not know who may benefit from hearing the wisdom which it contains. The aim of this document is to assist those who may need some release from stress and to invoke an efficacious remedy for the infection.

CORONA VIRUS - DO NOT FEAR IT BUT LOVE IT

Many people are becoming very stressed and worried by the corona virus which is ravaging almost every nation in the world. Yet despite the many adverse comments about it, the way to remove the stress and to conquer the virus is to learn how to love it.

This may seem to be an extremely difficult thing to do, especially for those who have lost a close relative, friend or colleague. We cannot bring those people back, but we can make life for those who still live to become free from fear and infection - through love.

Firstly we need to see, as many people already have, that there is a hidden message in this unprecedented event of the corona virus. In terms of the natural world this virus is a living creature. Hence it is as much a part of Mother Nature as we human beings are. Indeed all living and non-living things are part of Mother Nature.

Many people have learned to see Mother Nature in a very different light over the last decades, where the focus has been on how the human race is destroying Her balance and damaging Her environment. Some people are now saying that they believe Mother Nature is now striking back at the human race for its negligence of duty to Mother Nature and all her creatures. All these views are part of the picture, but few have seen how it is all joined up. To do this we need to link Mother Nature to the

Creator of the whole show. By this I do not wish to invoke a religious approach. Instead I have looked to the writings of mankind which are known to be the oldest on the planet. Those called Veda - which simply means "knowledge". Truly they are not a religion - but a philosophy of how to understand the whole creation in its mysterious and wonderful forms. This includes understanding the current event of corona virus.

Many great human beings have borrowed from the Vedas and have tried to teach mankind that his ways of living are contrary to Mother Nature. Such people as Shri Krishna, Jesus, Rumi and even Shakespeare. All were really great teachers who tried to teach the human race about the errors in its ways. None of these great people actually started a religion - but their teachings have remained universal and valuable for all time. However, generally mankind does not listen nor act on the advice given.

Hence I do not expect many to hear the message in this way of seeing the corona virus; which is affecting all our lives in one way or another. But here it is.

We should reflect on the history of holy interventions into human communities over the many thousands of years that we know this has happened. Rama and Krishna were here on this planet in the age prior to this dark age. Jesus, Rumi, the Buddha, and Shri Guru Deva (to name but a few) were all part of this Kali Yuga (dark age) - the age of spiritual darkness - or ignorance. We should reflect on the overall message which they gave to us. Which is basically, as human beings we should resist the temptations of - **seeking power** (fame and ego) - **seeking pleasure** (attraction of the senses) - and **seeking wealth** (attraction to material possessions). [these are errors of **soul** - **mind** and **body** in that order] It is not to say that we should not have any of these things - but that we should be content with what we have been given and not desire more of them.

It is **excess desire** for these things which has damaged Mother Nature's world. We are all prone to seek excess of the above three.

This next view may be too advanced for most of you. But it is the best way to see the current situation of the virus now attacking the whole human race. Therefore try to make effort to drop preconceived ideas.

If we truly see the corona virus we would see it as another manifestation of the Creator (through Mother Nature) - and that His message is simple - whatever control or power or wealth or economy or military prowess etc. etc. the human nations believe they had accrued - maybe

over centuries – these all became powerless - when a creature so small it cannot be seen – showed itself to have more power over them all.

Where else has such a tiny creature brought international travel almost to a halt. Whenever did something so small bring all nations on the earth virtually to their knees. If we do not see this as the power of the Creator - then we will never truly see what the message behind corona virus is. He has tried over many centuries through the great teachers mentioned above - to let the human race know where the real power is in the creation. But the human race does not hear the message and believes in its own power.

Those who welcome the corona virus and accept it into their life as the presence of the power of the Creator - **it will not do them any harm** – to love it and not be negative towards it is the true spiritual way. Because such a person sees the Lord Creator in all things. In this approach there is no need for prayer or fear, only for love.

It is amazing to see how much capacity the human race has shown that it can love others during this virus crisis. There are countless acts of great love which have come forth from so many people because of the effect of the corona virus. Hence it is true that the corona virus has invoked love.

For those who wish to remain free from fear and stress in relation to the virus, to love it is the **best vaccination** which can be applied. This cure is available now and dwells within the capacity of all human beings. Reflect deeply on this fact.

The true way to conquer the virus is to love it as part of Mother Nature.

I rest my case.

The beauty you see in the world comes from Him who exists within you.

Without His presence within, you would not see anything, even that beauty.

First know that your-Self is Him, then no one thing will seem to be more beautiful than any other thing. You will know that He is all things.

Then you have true Self-knowledge. This is the purpose of your life.

When you have finished with the worldly things, don't forget to remember yourself, and to forget the world. Otherwise in the end your life is truly empty.

To make your life full, study the scriptures which teach the above truth of life.

Have faith and trust that their knowledge will give you eternal peace.

Swami Vishnu Ananda Saraswati